

RESISTANCE WELDING OF CARBON FIBRE FABRIC REINFORCED POLYETHERIMIDE (CF FABRIC/PEI) COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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SUMMARY : This paper presents an experimental investigation of resistance welding of carbon fibre fabric reinforced polyetherimide composites (CF fabric/PEI) by resistance welding. An experiment apparatus was developed to carry out experiments which yield information on the processing parameters, such as current intensity, input energy, power, welding time and consolidation pressure. All of them can govern more or less the efficiency of the welding process. The heating element consisted of a single ply of CF fabric/PEI fabric prepreg. Experiments were conducted under displacement control. The quality of the welded samples was studied by using an ultrasonic, non-destructive evaluation technique (C-scan) as well as mechanical test (lap shear) program. Experimental results indicated that sufficient joining was obtained at power levels from 80 to 160 kW/m², under initial welding pressures varying from 0.15 to 0.40 MPa. The maximum lap shear strength achieved through resistance welding were equivalent to those of compression molded samples. The fracture surfaces of welded samples showed mostly cohesive failure or intralaminar failure. An optimum processing window was finally determined for the resistance welding of CF fabric/PEI composite system.

KEYWORDS: joining, composites, resistance welding, thermoplastic, carbon fibre, Polyetherimide

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites have been introduced as structural materials for high performance aerospace and industrial applications. High strain to failure, increased fracture toughness, better impact tolerance, short processing cycle time, infinite shelf life of prepreg, recyclability and reparability are some of the reasons cited for their growing popularity. The most important advantage of thermoplastics may lie in their potential for rapid, low-cost, mass production of reinforced composites. However, due to the deformation restriction of continuous fibre reinforcements, composite components with only relative simple geometry can be effectively produced from these materials. To make large and complex structures, several components must be jointed together. For this to happen it is very important to develop fast and reliable joining methods in the manufacturing and repairing of thermoplastic composites. The traditional joining methods are adhesive bonding and mechanical fastening. Adhesive joining is difficult for composites with thermoplastic matrix because of the difficulty of chemically bonding to the matrix. On the other hand, mechanically fastened joints are subjected to problems of stress concentration and damage of

the reinforcing fibres, especially for unidirectional fibre reinforced composites. Thermally welding may offer a solution to the problem of joining thermoplastic composite materials [1]. It eliminates problems of introducing another material into the bonding surface and the stress raising factors associated with mechanical fasteners [2].

This paper presents an experimental investigation of resistance welding of carbon fibre (CF) fabric reinforced polyetherimide (PEI) composites. The special interest is to develop a clear understanding of the effects of processing conditions on the structural and mechanical properties of the joint product. Resistance welding is a method for quickly heating and melting composites at the bond surface by passing electric current through a resistive element which is placed at the bond line and remains permanently there [3,4]. In the present study, an experimental apparatus was developed to carry out resistance welding. Processing parameters, such as welding pressure, input power level and welding time have been investigated. The heating element is a single ply of CF fabric/PEI prepreg. The graphite fibres in the heating element produce Joule heating when an electric current is passed through the element. The quality of welded surface was examined by non-destructive evaluation technique (C-Scan) and lap shear test. Experimental results indicated that sufficient bonding was obtained at power levels from 80 to 160 kW/m², under initial welding pressures varying from 0.15 to 0.40 MPa. The maximum lap shear strength achieved through resistance welding were equivalent to those of compression molded samples. The fracture surfaces of welded samples showed mostly cohesive failure or intralaminar failure. An optimum processing window was finally determined for the resistance welding of CF fabric/PEI composite system.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material

The material used in this study was solvent impregnated carbon fibre fabric reinforced polyetherimide (Ultem 1000) prepreg supplied by Ten Cate Advanced Composites, the Netherlands. The carbon fabric has a 5H satin woven construction. The prepreg has a resin content of 44.1 wt %. PEI is an amorphous polymer and has a glass transition temperature of about 217°C. During the solvent impregnation process some air was entrapped by the PEI polymer, which formed many tiny air bubbles on the surface of the prepreg. The cross-section micrograph of the CF/PEI prepreg shows that most of the PEI matrix (about 60%) remains outside the warp/weft fibre bundles and there exist a lot of voids in the middle of the fibre bundle, especially at the contact area between the warp and weft fibre bundles. Consolidation of the laminates was performed using a small steel mold with a rectangular cavity (250 mm x 150 mm) and a laboratory hot press. The following conditions were used in the preparation of pre-consolidated laminate: molding temperature 320°C, pressure 2.0 MPa and holding time of 15 min [5]. Each laminate contained 10 layers of the CF/PEI prepreg; this led to a thickness of about 2.6 mm for a fully consolidated laminate. Specimen with a dimension of 100 mm long and 25 mm wide were then machined from the panel with a diamond saw. All bond surfaces were polished slightly with sand paper and cleaned with acetone prior to welding. In addition, compression molded lap shear samples were also prepared to provide a basis for comparison.

Heating Element

Since the heating element remains embedded at the interface in this process, it is important that it is compatible with the composites to be jointed. Therefore a single CF fabric/PEI prepreg was used as the resistive element, taking advantage of the semi-conducting nature of the graphite fibres. To make heating element with good impregnation/consolidation quality, single CF fabric/PEI prepreg was also compression moulded according to the above mentioned conditions. To introduce rich matrix layer in the heating element, single CF fabric/PEI prepreg sandwiched between two PEI film (with a thickness of 0.076 mm) was also prepared. The heating element was then cut from the pre-consolidated single prepreg with a dimension of 120 mm long in the warp fibre direction and 12.5 mm wide in the weft fibre direction. To introduce current to the warp carbon fibre, the matrix was burnt from both ends of the prepreg (approximately 40 mm at each end).

Experimental Set-up

The experimental set-up used for the resistance welding is shown in Figure 1. It consists of a stack of material to be welded, the electrical components and an universal testing machine. Direct current used for welding is supplied by a power transformer with a maximum current output of 30 A and a maximum voltage output of 30 V. The stack of material to be welded consisted of two 10 ply pre-consolidated laminate and a heating element. Two couples of brass blocks bolted together to provide contact pressure were selected as clamp connectors for the heating element. It was found that the maximum contact resistance between the brass clamps and the fibres is only 8% of the total resistance of the heating element, when the clamped fibre length is more than 20 mm. Under this condition it gets a more homogeneous heating of the heating element. Two blocks of spruce wood were chosen as insulators, helping to reduce heat losses and to provide alignment of the samples to be welded.

Figure 1. Experimental set-up

The important parameters for the welding process are the power P (in kW/m^2) and the input energy E (in kJ/m^2), which are supplied at the welding interface per unit area [3]:

$$P = I^2 R / LW \quad (1)$$

$$E = P t \quad (2)$$

where R is the resistance of the heating element (in Ohm), I the electrical current put into the system (in Ampere), P the power (in kW/m^2) and t the electrified time (in second); L and W are the length and width (both in meter) of the welding area.

Mechanical Testing

Lap shear tensile test (ASTM D1002) was performed at room temperature for both resistance welded and compression moulded specimens. The test specimen was 200 mm in length and 25 mm in width with a overlap length of 12 mm. Three or two replicates were tested for each set of process parameters. Before testing the welded samples were polished by 0.5 mm on each side so that the edge irregularities obtained during the welding process due to transverse matrix flow and squeeze effects could be removed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demarcation of Heating Element

Figure 2. Resistance of CF fabric/PEI in relation to its dimension

The resistance of a material is directly proportional to its length and inversely proportional to its cross section. It is assumed that the CF fabric/PEI prepreg has a constant fibre volume fraction in the warp fibre direction, a constant thickness and the fibres are homogeneously distributed across the width, so that the resistance R of the prepreg should be calculated as follows:

$$R = r L/W \quad (3)$$

where L is the length of the prepreg, W its width, and r the specific resistance of the material (at constant thickness of the heating element). To obtain the value of r , the resistance of single CF fabric/PEI prepreps of various length, but a constant width of 45 mm, and of prepreps having various width, but a constant length of 135 mm have been measured. Both sets of data result in linear curves when plotting the R values vs. L and $1/W$, respectively (Figure 2). Note that the resistance of the connection between clamps and fibres is already removed by

extrapolation! From the slope of both curves, a mean value of 0.242 for the coefficient r can be obtained. By using this value, the resistance of any CF/PP heating element with known length and width can be calculated.

Effect of Power Level on Welding Process

Preliminary experiments were performed in order to determine the maximum and minimum input power levels necessary to carry out resistance welding economically. The conditions required for the minimum power level were that 100% of the welding region be melted within a time of 120 seconds. This was tested by examining fractured welding surface. According to the results of some trial and error experiments, the minimum accepted power level was found to be 80 kW/m^2 . It was noted that at a power level of as low as 60 kW/m^2 , it took a too long time (about 3-4 min) until the whole surface could be melted, and at the same time the samples became very soft and flexible, and could not maintain their original geometry. It implied that most of the energy got lost by heating up the bulk samples and the surroundings. It is known that besides heating and melting the matrix at the interface, the quantity of heat produced by the heating element gets partially lost into the bulk interior of the samples to be welded and into the environment as a result of convection, radiation and conduction. The longer the welding time is, the greater is the heat loss. At high power levels, on the other hand, the melting time can be kept short, because the heating rate is rather high. If, however, the power level is too high (200 kW/m^2), the matrix can be burnt away resulting in fibre oxidation, which reduces the joining efficiency and increases the resistance of the heating element. For this reason, the following experiments were carried out between the two power limits, i.e. 80 to 160 kW/m^2 .

Effect of Welding Pressure

Figure 3. Effect of welding pressure on lap shear strength

When the thermoplastic matrix melts, stored elastic energy in the fibres is released which can lead to warpage and deconsolidation [6]. Therefore, parts to be welded must be properly supported by external pressure during the welding process. The effect of initial welding pressure on lap shear strength of welded sample is shown in Figure 3, in which the lap strength of compression molded sample is also shown as a bench-mark. All samples were welded at the same power level of 118 kW/m^2 and an input energy of 3933 kJ/m^2 . The experimental results show that low initial welding pressures (0.02-0.05 MPa) resulted in weak joints. The reason is as follows: if the initial welding pressure is low, then the consolidation

pressure is not high enough to suppress the elastic deformation of the fibres and to remove air voids at the interface. The results of ultrasonic investigation (C-scan) of these samples welded at different pressures verified the assumption. The initial welding pressure suitable for the experiments in this study was found to be in the range of 0.15 - 0.40 MPa.

Effect of PEI Film

The mechanism governing the formation of interply bonds has been established as autohesion or selfdiffusion [7] and the bond line thickness has a significant effect on the final mechanical property of the welded sample [4]. Figure 4 shows the lap shear strength of samples welded with two kind of heating elements, i.e. heating element with PEI film and without PEI film. It can be seen that the lap shear strength of samples welded with PEI film heating element are about 20 to 30% higher than that of samples manufactured with heating element without PEI film. The PEI film can produce a thin layer of PEI, about 0.05 mm, on both side of the heating element. The softening and deformation of these thin PEI layers can effectively promote the intimate contact between the welding surface, which is of benefit to the diffusion of macromolecules across the interface. Therefore, the welding experiments were carried out using heating element with PEI film.

Figure 4. Lap shear strength of CF fabric/PEI samples welded with/without PEI (input power 140 kW/m²)

Input Energy in Relationship to Power Level

From the results of section 3.2 input power levels of 80, 118, 140 and 160 kW/m², respectively, were chosen for the resistance welding. The other parameter varied in these experiments was the electrified time, which controls the amount of thermal energy supplied to the welding interface by the heating element. The lap shear strengths of samples welded at these four power levels are plotted in Figures 4 to 7 as a function of the thermal energy released by the heating element. The value in the black box represents the lap shear strength of a compression molded specimen. From these figures the following general trends can be seen: (1) the lap shear strength of the welded specimens approaches a peak level with increasing welding energy and then decreases slightly for each power level; (2) the energy needed for the peak value of lap shear strength decreases dramatically with increasing power

level. (3) except for the power level of 160 kW/m^2 , the maximum lap shear strengths achieved at the other three power levels approached up to 95% of the lap shear strength value of the compression molded specimen.

Figure 5. Lap shear strength of CF fabric/PEI composite welded at power level of 80 kW/m^2)

Figure 6. Lap shear strength of CF fabric/PEI composite welded at power level of 118 kW/m^2)

Figure 7. Lap shear strength of CF fabric/PEI composite welded at power level of 160 kW/m^2)

The welded regions were examined by both an ultrasonic technique and fracture surface analysis. The latter could be made after the lap shear test. The fracture surfaces of welded parts show that the portion of fractured area increased clearly with increasing welding energy, and this is in agreement with the observation made by the ultrasonic technique. Each specimen was examined optically to determine the mode of failure. It was found that there were two distinct modes of failure, i.e. intralaminar and interfacial failure. Intralaminar failure, as shown in Figure 8 (a), was considered to occur when fracture occurred either within the bulk structure of the composites, within the heating element or within both of them. Interfacial failure (Figure 8 b) resulted in the fracture at the interface the between heating element and the composite. All samples shown in Figure 4-7 show a change in failure mode from interfacial to intralaminar failure with increasing welding energy. At low input power level, a greater amount of energy produced by the heating element gets lost into both bulk specimen and environment, because the heating rate of the interface at low power level is much lower than that at high power level [8]. Therefore, a longer electrified time or more energy will be needed at lower power level than at higher power level for melting the same amount of matrix at the interface. If the electrified time at a given power level is too short, the thermal energy released by the heating element is not enough to melt the polymer matrix at the bonding surfaces, thus leading to weak or no joint. A situation like this can be seen from the low lap shear strength achieved with low input welding energy in these figures, which shows that the failure occurs at the interface between the laminate and the heating element because of incomplete bonding; this resulted in a lap shear strength of only 10 to 30% of that of compression molded sample. With increasing welding time, more polymer matrix of the contacting surfaces will be molten; this increases the welding area and leads to a change of failure mode from interfacial to intralaminar failure. This is associated with a higher lap shear strength, for example, at an input energy of 3933 kJ/m² and an input power level of 118 kW/m² (Figure 6), the lap shear strength is 30 MPa, which is close to the value of compression molded sample.

The maximum lap shear strength achieved with power level of 160 kW/m² is 86% of that of benchmark. The reasons are to be believed due to (a) the interface and/or interphase between matrix and fibre has been damaged to some extent by passing electric current through fibres [8] and (b) a relatively short period of dwell time of polymer matrix at its molten state. The latter factor prevents the polymer chains to penetrate and entangle sufficiently into the adjacent interface, which results in a partially diffused interface.

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study on the subject of resistance welding of pre-consolidated, carbon fibre fabric reinforced polyetherimide (CF fabric/PEI) was successfully performed. An optimum initial welding pressure was found to be in the range of 0.15 - 0.40 MPa.

As a conclusion, the optimum processing window for resistance welding of CF fabric /PEI composite based on a critical level of lap shear strength can be evaluated from the experimental results. Assuming 86% lap shear strength of the benchmark (compression

Figure 8. Failure types of lap shear test

molded sample) is the critical mechanical property of the joint. The relationship between processing conditions required to reach this desired level of strength can be illustrated as a form of a processing window in Figure 9. The points in this diagram represent the welding conditions used in this experiment. The ordinate represents the input power (in kW/m^2), the abscissa the welding time (or electrified time), and the product of both of them results in the input energy (in kJ/m^2), illustrated in form of equivalent energy lines. The entire figure is divided into five sections. Section II and section III represent the limits for the input power. If the power is too high the matrix can be burnt away and decomposed. Owing to the low heating rate at the interface and great loss of thermal energy into the bulk specimen and the surroundings, on the other hand, low power causes too much energy loss or insufficient joining quality. Area (I) is the processing window, in which good bonding can be achieved at a power level range from 80 kJ/m^2 to 160 kJ/m^2 . The mechanical properties of these joints (lap shear strength) are equivalent to 86% of that of the compression molded base line. Inside this area the input energy needed for sufficient welding decreases with increasing power level. Too much thermal energy (or too long electrified time) results in a great movement of fibres at the interface and unsteady geometry of the welded specimens because of their softening (area V). If the input thermal energy is not sufficient enough (e.g. due to a too short electrified time) in order to melt the matrix at the interface, it produces only weak or even no bonding at all (area IV).

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Figure 9. Processing window for resistance welding of CF fabric/PEI composites

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